

Budgeting Controls and Client Satisfaction under Last Planner System¹

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Abstract

The relationship between the Last Planner System (LPS), budgetary controls, and client satisfaction within Uganda's construction industry occupies the central position of this paper. Persistent challenges such as cost overruns, project delays, and inconsistent client satisfaction underscore the need for effective project management strategies. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, and data were collected from 315 employees across 56 construction firms registered with the Uganda National Association of Building and Civil Engineering Contractors. Quantitative analysis using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, and linear regression revealed that LPS implementation significantly reduces waste and improves process reliability. However, LPS's direct emphasis on budgeting exhibited a modest negative correlation, highlighting the necessity for integrated planning and financial control approaches. Notably, robust budgetary controls aligned with LPS principles were found to positively influence clients' satisfaction by ensuring timely and quality project delivery. The findings emphasise the need to harmonise production planning systems with financial controls to optimise performance and client outcomes in construction projects. This research contributes to the discourse on lean construction management by demonstrating the synergistic benefits of combining LPS with effective budgetary practices in emerging economies, client satisfaction and timely project delivery.

Keywords

Last Planner System, Budgetary Controls, Client Satisfaction, Lean Construction, Project Management.

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Background

The application of LPS in the construction industry across the globe is increasing per day, but information about its association with budgetary control and client satisfaction is limited. This becomes the main issue which this paper partly seeks to address. Ideally, budgeting is a process through which a company prepares detailed projections of the future. In simple terms, it is balancing expenses with income (Obi & Ph, 2015). Budgetary controls are therefore methods employed in the management of costs through which a budget is prepared (Oyebode, 2018). It is one of the highly recommended budgetary controls that effectively guides managers in the allocation of resources (Gulpenko et al., 2017). In a construction company, budgetary control is characterised by a budget for the purpose of business, revisions of occurring conditions, and comparison of budgeted and actual outcomes (Kruger et al., 2017). It has immense significance to develop horizontal and vertical structures of a company, as well as impact the financial and economic purposes of business (Jayalakshmi & Shetty, 2023).

The fact that construction companies are characterised by long production cycles not for tomorrow or a month means that the budget plan mechanism becomes a means to control market context and possible competition (Espacios et al., 2017). It is for this reason that budget control remains one of the most important tools for a construction company and maximisation of profits. As indicated by Matsoso and Nyathi (2021), budgeting tools have positive benefits from perception and value controls. However, it has not been associated with LPS and client satisfaction. According to Akeke and Akaniniene (2024), unless companies allow budget implementation and evaluation, their success in day-to-day and future activities is limited. The failure to apply budget control as a tool hinders coordination, evaluation and financial performance (Mutabari & Warui, 2023). Moreover, it also has antagonistic consequences, including cost overruns and increased delays on construction projects. Yet, if the tool is adopted effectively, it enhances success in terms of timely delivery of the construction projects (Chinedum, 2019).

On the other hand, a client's satisfaction is the overall experience and sentiment of the consumer when it comes to consumption of the products, services or any item provided by the company (Mittal et al., 2023). It is also referred to as the client's response to the consultation experience by evaluating the perceived discrepancy between first expectations and actual acquired goods or services (Segoro & Limakrisna, 2020). It is normally the last stage in selling products since it ensures behavioural reputation, royalty and constant business performance. In the realm of construction industries and delivering projects, a client comprises the whole journey of what is intended to be delivered and actual delivery.

According to Rahman (2015), client satisfaction is the general goal of a contractor to meet clients' expectations. Thus, the knowledge about what satisfies expectations of clients is important to a contractor since outcomes must be measured in numerous ways. These include service quality, budgetary follow-ups, communication skills, security and protection issues, adherence to schedules, skills of an individual officer in office and approaches towards a client that enable them to appreciate the delivery of the project.

Egemen (2022) has noted that achieving clients' satisfaction is paramount, and it has been the main focus of the construction market since it is the only way to keep a company in today's progressive operation. Therefore, design must suit the client's perception of the delivered project. Hussaini and Kachalla (2022) show that the needs and satisfaction of clients in construction industries play a suggestive role in whether the project will be successful. This makes client satisfaction a dimension of quality to be designed. Owing to this background, the paper aims at assessing the association between LPS with budgetary controls and the client's satisfaction.

Last Planner System (LPS)

The Last Planner System entered into building and construction in the 1990s as a system for project production and delivery control (Limenih et al., 2022). The form of management could not lead to effective production and delivery of projects as per clients' satisfaction. The need for project control remained costly, as companies sought to schedule, align project scope and monitor progress towards targets (Hamzeh & Aridi, 2020). The production or construction control was sought to steer towards targets, to do what had been planned, but whenever it became hard, companies would seek the alternative to achieve targets and deliver projects (Kumar et al., 2024). This, however, could not reach client satisfaction due to inconveniences in the due process.

Since 1992, LPS came into the system with specific attention to attaining better results in work plans, and this made it possible to be extended to construction design (Hussaini & Kachalla, 2022). The move led to improvement of productivity, reliability and the general flow. Since then, LPS has been used to achieve current and final projects. LPS has enabled companies to abandon the traditional approach towards the realisation of building projects and new thinking. This has been achieved through the budgetary controls (Chiu & Cousins, 2020).

Karaz et al. (2024) assert that for effective and successive construction projects, LPS must embrace controls like budgeting. This leads to working within the main aim of waste elimination and effective delivery of the final project. It also results in a reduction of tasks performed, completion rate, cost reduction, possible mitigations and construction planning. The policy makers are further attracted to seeking possible approaches to budgeting within construction companies due to its accrued benefits.

Kudrekodlu and Venkatesan (2021) state that while lean technology has the potential to create possible circumstances attracting all stakeholders in building and construction phases, it is LPS that is responsible for project delivery and the client's satisfaction. LPS improves reliable strategies for possible plans, future imaginations, and transparent plans, as well as accuracy in time to deliver projects, effectiveness and efficiency in high-ranking managers, recruiting and skilling of relevant employees, involvement of stakeholders, and reduction of construction barriers (Kumar et al., 2024). It also improves process implementation, translates projects into success, and instills confidence in a company by various stakeholders.

According to More and Fulse (2021), LPS manages the relationships, conversations and commitments of workers by enabling programme and production planning decisions. These further enable collaboration of officers at the lower ranks towards construction and production. To Hussaini and Kachalla (2022), LPS is the possible option for companies to manage clients' expectations and

satisfaction. Once clients' needs are properly identified and addressed through budgeting, optimum satisfaction must be achieved.

Kumar et al. (2024) emphasised that LPS is one of the best approaches in planning, as well as processes of production and regulations. These fall under the main theme of LC as the mainstream. For effective and expected results from the LC, a construction company must seek possible measures to apply what the LPS commands. These include automated planning and controls, if possible, as long as the concepts of should, can and will are maintained in the project control. These enable the mastery of the whole project, intermediate projects and weekly programmes.

Limenih et al. (2022) found that the success of the road construction project on Addis Ababa Road was a result of LPS applied as part of Lean Construction Technology (LCT) with budget control which was differentiated from local budgeting. In fact, LPS was applied to realise solutions and as a tool that attracted groups of people to control production and delivery units. In the first instance, LPS was used to prioritise expected barriers in the project, implementation of the schedule, and making a quality and valued choice approach, in which frameworks can be scheduled. Limenih et al. (2022) also reveal that LPS enables the company to rank the barriers based on materials applications. These include labour force and internal and external involvement of stakeholders. The most beneficial were ranked as time benefits, cost, quality and management benefits.

Lappalainen et al. (2022) go on to state that LPS is a production control which the LCT has applied to attain good results in terms of improving labour productivity, collaboration of employees and management, and continuous work schedules. Such an assertion is similar to what Chiu & Cousins (2020) state: that LPS enables project team members to come together and plan for collective goals so that there is improvement in flows and reliability. Lastly, Hamzeh and Aridi (2020) indicate that LPS increases reliability of weekly work planning through master or phase schedules and lookahead planning. As a result, the company achieved task anticipated (TA) and task made ready (TMR) faster and increased stakeholders' participation (SP). It was from this perspective that this paper is presented while assess the association of LPS and budgetary controls as well as clients' satisfaction

Methods and sampling

A cross-section design was adopted as per Wang and Cheng (2020a). The choice for cross-section stems from the design of the construction companies from Kampala Capital City, with an assumption that selected employees would be knowledgeable of LPS, budgetary controls and client satisfaction. The companies in construction were considered main stakeholders at national and international levels. In Uganda, registered companies were 111 at the time of the study. These have been put under the UNABCEC as of August 2020; only 56 were selected

The classification adopted was based on company annual turnover and experience in the construction industry. The highest classification was A-1, while A-5 was at the lowest position. Despite having staff and supportive staff, ranging from 10 to 60 employees, knowledgeable employees were selected. Thus, the primacy of purposive and simple random sampling techniques (Mulisa, 2022).

A survey questionnaire was developed to interrogate LPS, budgetary control and the client's satisfaction. The Likert scale of four (4) was selectively chosen for the purpose and later applied in

collecting data. The questions were intended to capture the appropriateness found in controls and the extent to which LPS (which is applied by the companies selected) leads to satisfaction of clients in the due process of construction and project delivery. In order to maintain quality, a pilot study was conducted around Kampala, and 0.923 reliability was obtained on a scale of five under the large scale

Analysis

Quantitative data analysis was done using version 26 of the Scientific Package for the Social Scientists. The application of Microsoft Excel was inevitable to arrange information well in accordance with variables and codes. It was necessary to use SPSS in order to proofread and remove other errors as well as make the work standardised. First, the descriptive summary background is provided by means of data collected. This was followed by presenting skewness and kurtosis to determine the normal distribution of data (Ali et al., 2021). Statistically, the calculation for the two follows the following formulas:

$$Z_{skewness} = \frac{Skewness}{\sqrt{\frac{6}{N}}}$$

Whereby, N = sample size; Z = calculations from kurtosis value with the following formula

$$Z_{kurtosis} = \frac{Kurtosis}{\sqrt{\frac{24}{N}}}$$

Normality is therefore obtained when the value of Z is equal to or less than the identified critical value. Once the value of Z is beyond the identified or stated value, it makes the distribution neither normal nor abnormal. Normality is obtained with the level of 99% at the 99% confidence level. Once $Z_{skewness}$ and $Z_{kurtosis}$ are below ± 2.58 at the level of 0.01 and ± 1.96 at 0.05 value, then there must be concurrence with the normality of the data (Taber, 2018).

In the analysis, the Pearson correlation coefficient was applied. Under this, r was used in the illustration of data to justify a link or linear relationship of the variables. Modelling was later made using linear regression with the summary and ANOVA factor analysis to illustrate the variables.

Results

Kurtosis and skewness were used to establish the normal distribution of the data from respective companies.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of normality and linearity distribution of results

	N	Mean	Std D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Gender	315	1.30	.460	.869	-1.253
Age group	315	2.53	.702	.126	-0.247
Education level	315	3.30	1.034	-0.442	-.286
Duration	315	2.38	.897	.072	-0.761
Knowledge of LPS	315	2.24	.789	-.456	-1.255
Embraced LPS	315	2.37	.578	-.254	-.712
Clients' satisfaction	315	2.07	1.138	.358	-1.467

In accordance with Table 1, the mean (\pm) scores were above ± 1.96 apart from the \pm of gender. There is also variance in values of kurtosis and skewness in the distribution for the background variables as presented. Whereas the values of kurtosis and skewness are presented negatively and some positively, all the \pm scores were less than the critical value of ± 2.58 . Owing to this analysis, one can equally infer that there was probably a normal distribution of data or variables used for this case. In fact, the mean (\pm) of 2.53 for the age group is a clear indication of the normal distribution of age ranges that were selected to respond to concerns of LPS interrogated. This is justified by Coakes & Steed (2003), who justified normality with such findings or calculations run.

Modeling relationship between LPS and budgetary control

Results presented in Table 2 indicate that there is a relationship between LPS and budgetary controls, and the correlations have been explained in the preceding sentences.

Table 2: Correlation between LPS and budgetary controls in construction industry

		Controls flows	Emphasizes budgeting	Reduces wastes in time
LPS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.214**	.117*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.038
	N	315	315	315
Controls flows	Pearson Correlation	-.214**	1	.004
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.942
	N	315	315	315
Emphasizes budgeting	Pearson Correlation	.117*	.004	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.038	.942	
	N	315	315	315
Reduces wastes in time	Pearson Correlation	.235**	-0.059	.206**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.297	.000
	N	315	315	315
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

The correlative analysis indicates the sample, $n = 315$, was used; the correlation is $r(315) = -.214^{**}$, $p < 0.01$. An indication of a significantly negative link or association between LPS and its emphasis on budgeting. On correlating LPS with budgetary control to reduce waste in time $r(315) = .117^*$, $p > 0.01$ and reduction of waste in terms of inputs $r(315) = .235^{**}$, $p < 0.01$, there is a relationship which is significant on reduction at input as compared to reduction of waste in time. The model summary is presented as:

Model Summary				
Model	R	R. Square	Adjusted R. Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.317 ^a	.101	.092	1.155
a. Predictors: (Constant), reduces waste in terms of inputs, emphasizes budgeting, reduces wastes in relation to time				

The model summary shows that R² was .101, which is translated to mean that LPS would explain 11% of budgetary controls from the construction companies. Under ANOVA, the factor analysis and significance are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: The ANOVA Analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	46.417	3	15.472	11.606	.000 ^b
	Residual	414.599	311	1.333		
	Total	461.016	314			
a. Dependent Variable: LPS controls flows						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Budget reduces waste in terms of inputs, emphasizes budgeting, reduces wastes in relation to time						

ANOVA analysis in Table 3 indicates the linearity of LPS and budgeting F (1, 314) 11.606, with $p < 0.01$. This implied that a unit change in LPS caused a proportionate change in budgetary controls. The coefficient explanations are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: The Coefficients of the variables

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.206	.316		10.156	.000
	Emphasizes budgeting	-.209	.056	-.202	-3.753	.000
	Reduces wastes in relation to time	.089	.065	.075	1.367	.173
	Reduces waste in terms of inputs	.280	.074	.207	3.763	.000
a. Dependent Variable: LPS controls flows						

The coefficients of regression show the Beta = -.202, $p < 0.05$ for emphasis on budgeting; Beta = .075, $p > 0.05$ for reduction of wastes in time and Beta = .207, $p < 0.05$ for reduction of waste in terms of input which reveal that there is a relation between LPS and budgetary controls. Apart from the reduction of waste in terms of time, the rest of the relationships were also significant.

Besides the regression model illustrated, histogram and linear normal plots were applied to indicate the position of the analysed variables. Importantly, the budgetary measures or control were used as dependent variables while LPS was the independent variable. From the measurements of independent variables, the model was constructed. The first model consists of control of flows, emphasising budgeting, reducing waste in time and reducing waste in terms of inputs as dependent variables.

Figure 1: Normality test of using budgetary controls

Figure 1 contains standardised residuals as per the regression analysis that has been made. Under this, the budgetary control is presented as a dependent variable. Visually, the histogram and its curve are normal. Social scientists have asserted that once the number of visual observances is more than 200, there is normality of the distributed standardised residuals. In such circumstances, the assumption of normality becomes justified (Bartlett et al., 2001). This is also illustrated in Figure 2.

Line graph for Normal Plot of Regression Standardized budgetary controls' residual

Figure 2: Normality plots of budgetary controls under linear regression model graph

Figure 2 indicates a linear modelling to prove the linearity of budgetary controls' variables under the LPS. Thus, the importance of LPS in the construction companies.

Modeling relationship between LPS and clients' satisfaction

The study also analysed the relationship between LPS and clients' satisfaction on various issues under the construction management from Kampala Capital. Results of correlation and subsequent modelled parameters have been presented in Table 6.

Table 5: Relationship between LPS and clients' satisfaction in construction companies

		Satisfies clients	Enables delivery faster	Leads to quality work
LPS	Pearson Correlation	1	.006	.173**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.917	.002
	N	315	315	315
Satisfies clients	Pearson Correlation	.006	1	.122*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.917		.031
	N	315	315	315
Enables delivery faster	Pearson Correlation	.173**	.122*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.031	
	N	315	315	315
Leads to quality work	Pearson Correlation	.101	-.017	.009
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.073	.769	.867
	N	315	315	315
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Table 5 shows n = 315; the sample was used, and correlation $r(315) = .006$, $p > 0.01$ is for enabling faster delivery; $.173^{**}$, $p < 0.01$ for LPS leading to quality work for clients and reducing waste to zero level at $.101^{**}$, $p > 0.01$. These results indicate a mostly positive relationship between APS and the clients' satisfaction with the construction companies. The model summary is presented as:

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.200 ^a	.040	.031	1.172
a. Predictors: (Constant), LPS reduces wastes to zero, leads to quality work, enables delivering tasks faster in time				

The model summary shows that R^2 was .040, which is translated to mean that the application of LPS in the construction companies is well explained by 4% of clients' satisfaction. Under ANOVA, the factor analysis and significance are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: The ANOVA analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.869	3	5.956	4.334	.005 ^b
	Residual	427.452	311	1.374		
	Total	445.321	314			
a. Dependent Variable: LPS satisfies clients						
b. Predictors: (Constant), LPS reduces wastes to zero, leads to quality work, enables delivering tasks faster in time						

ANOVA analysis indicates the linearity between corporate governance roles and employee satisfaction F (1, 314) 4.334, with $p < 0.01$. This implied that a unit change in LPS caused a proportionate change in clients' satisfaction. The coefficient explanations are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: The Coefficients of variables analyzed

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.441	.334		7.309	.000
	Enables delivery faster in time	-.017	.069	-0.014	-0.244	.808
	Leads to quality work	.212	.068	.174	3.108	.002
	Reduces wastes to zero level	.103	.058	.099	1.789	.075
a. Dependent Variable: LPS satisfies clients						

The coefficients of regression show Beta = -.014, $p > 0.05$ for delivering projects faster in time; Beta = .174, $p < 0.05$ for leading to quality work; and .099, $p > 0.05$ for reducing waste to zero. In general, there is a relationship between LPS and clients' satisfaction, although various variables have different interpretations.

A histogram and linear normal plots were used to indicate the position of independent variables under clients' satisfaction while LPS was the independent variable. From the measurements of independent variables, the model was linearly constructed. The model consists of satisfying clients, enabling delivery of projects faster, leading to quality work for clients, and reducing waste up to zero per percent which pleases clients.

Figure 3: Normality test of client's level of satisfaction

Figure 3 indicates the actual results of regression standardised results using the client's level of satisfaction as a dependant variable of the study. The visual observation also shows that there was normality. As mentioned earlier, once observation values exceed 200, normality of the standardised residual is declared. This is followed with an assertion that the data satisfied the normality assumption (Bartlett et al., 2001). This can be as well presented under normal plots as presented in figure 4.

Line graph for Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized client's satisfaction residual

Figure 4: Normality plots of client's satisfaction under linear regression model graph

As indicated in figure 4, linear modelling for dependent variables proves the linearity of the client's satisfaction variables under LPS. This shows the importance of LPS in the construction.

Discussions

This article shows that there is a relationship between LPS and budgetary controls as discussed with particular variables, which is significant. The variables in question include control flows, emphasising budgeting, reducing waste in time and reduction of waste in terms of inputs. The variables are forms of controls that are under budgeting. As indicated by Karaz et al. (2024), effective application of budgetary

controls remains noble for successive and timely delivery of projects. Whereas some construction companies and individual contractors endeavour to come up with budgets, there are few that follow them (Matsoso & Nyathi, 2021). This failure to implement what has been included in the budget becomes a source for loose management and lack of controls. This becomes a source of delayed finishing of projects and delivery as well. On the other hand, companies and individual contacts that implement or work according to their budgets eliminate waste and effectively deliver final projects in time. Such construction companies and contracts reduce in tasks performed since budget becomes a tool to identify certain human resources to various tasks and directs finishing one contract before starting a second contract. This, therefore, is an indication that contractors implementing various contracts would be the source of delays, collapse of constructions and unsuccessful projects.

Through budgeting as a tool for controls, there is cost reduction of procured construction items, possible mitigation measures in case there is unwanted input, and construction planning that is strategic in nature for effective delivery of the project. According to Oyeboode (2018), a budget is applied as a management approach to control costs and guide managers in the allocation of resources. This form allocation becomes a basis for reducing waste at a certain time of construction as well as inputs (Ssali et al., 2022). The immense significance accrued from budgeting essentially develops the company and individual contractors horizontally and vertically. It also impacts financial use and economic purposes of business in a construction company (Jayalakshmi & Shetty, 2023).

Results indicate that the application of LPS is explained in terms of 11% of budgetary controls from the construction companies or individual constructors. As presented by Espacios et al. (2017), construction companies are characterised by long production cycles, not for tomorrow or a month; budget controls become an important tool to explain the use of LPS in relation to 11%. In the short and long run, construction companies and contractors that follow budgeting, maximisation of profits is an outcome for sticking to the budget. To Akeke and Akaniniene (2024), it is clear that unless companies implement budgets and evaluate their activities based on what has been budgeted, the success and delivery of projects in day-to-day and future activities are limited. This limitation is experienced with increased waste and incomplete projects on time (Chinedum, 2019).

Kumar et al. (2024) show the similarity between results and literature by confessing that LPS is one of the best production planning approaches with a control system. This control is implemented through a budget that comes with various policies regulating the activities and actions of managers and construction workers. In due course, time becomes an important factor in the commanding system due to budgeting. The wastes are reduced in case they are not eliminated; employees are directed to work in accordance with schedules, and output waste becomes no more as managers and construction workers focus on delivery.

The situation in applying budgeting under LPS is beneficial to clients who seek to benefit from or enjoy delivered projects. Indeed, clients become satisfied as construction companies or contractors deliver the projects faster, witness quality work and the reduction of waste to zero level. This is similar to what Hussaini and Kachalla (2022) reveal: that LPS is an option for companies to manage clients' expectations and satisfaction. As clients become satisfied with the project deliveries, their propensity to

attract their friends and to refer to such companies and contractors increases. This leads to horizontal and vertical expansion of the companies or contractors implementing what has been budgeted. Indeed, Segoro and Limakrisna (2020) state that when such a circumstance is attained within a company, there is a change of behaviour among clients, especially those that have obtained good services. Thus, a client's satisfaction is the whole journey to what companies plan and budget for, in the short and long run, especially the actual delivery of the projects to them.

Literature has shown that a company or contractor needs to be knowledgeable about what satisfies clients and their expectations (Rahman, 2015). This has been proved right since the outcomes must be measured in numerous ways. These were among the results of this study. Egemen (2022) adds that achieving a client's satisfaction is the most important need that keeps a company in today's progressive operation. It is the duty of construction companies and contractors to design approaches suiting a client's delivery project based on time and schedules.

Conclusion

The application of LPS by a construction company or contractor is not a one-way approach; rather, it comes with other demands such as budgetary controls intended to increase management methods, work schedules among workers, timely project delivery and satisfaction of clients. The company or a constructor must seek and utilise possible strategies that lead to the client's satisfaction.

Emphasising LPS together with budgeting enhances project planning and communication about current, upcoming and intended tasks to a company. This commands the optimisation of resource allocation, minimising the waste which leads to increased efficiency in delivering projects just in time. Besides, this article recommends the use LPS alongside budgeting to enable company managers to have assurance in their communication and collaboration with task-teams on issues regarding finance. This will motivate the team towards effectiveness, responsiveness, efficiency and transparency.

The focus for efficiency is instrumental towards reducing waste since the company managers will be able to identify and eliminate challenges within the project to be delivered to clients. In brief, the use of LPS and budgeting will streamline the task flows and reduce delays towards project delivery. Additionally, there is a need to apply both LPS and budget as companies seek continuous improvements, training teams from past to new experiences needed in planning and optimising future projects. In doing so, there will be efficient use of resources in scheduled time and greater probability for the company.

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